

TENSILE STRENGTH ENHANCEMENT OF CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITES BY DISPERSING CARBON BLACK

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1 Introduction

Carbon/carbon composites (C/C composites) are lightweight and maintain their thermo-mechanical properties such as modulus, strength, and toughness, even in ultra-high temperature environments above 2300 K. Due to this advantage, they have been applied, for example, to rocket nozzles and heat shields in aerospace industry. Application fields of C/C composites, however, have been limited because of the drawbacks, one of which is relatively low tensile strength compared with polymer matrix composites. As shown in Fig.1, the ratio of actual tensile strength of C/C composites to that predicted by the rule of mixture (ROM) (hereinafter referred to “*fiber efficiency, Y*”) is no more than 30~40%, indicating only a fraction of potential fiber strength is used for reinforcing C/C composites; it is fully used in case of plastic matrix composites, though [1].

It is well known that laminated C/C composites are fractured in a brittle manner, and flat fracture surfaces are usually observed where fibers and matrix are fractured in the same fracture plane. Previous study [1] showed that strong fiber/matrix interfacial strength is one of the critical properties decreasing the fiber efficiency of C/C composites. On the contrary, it was shown that monofilament C/C composites, which are reinforced by carbon monofilament, have identical strength to that of carbon fiber itself independent of heat treatment temperature as shown in Fig.2 [2]. The fracture occurred in a “*fiber pull-out*” manner, suggesting low fiber/matrix interfacial strength. These results suggest that possible improvement in the fiber efficiency of C/C composites by reducing interfacial strength.

Fig.1 Fiber efficiency and temperature dependence of laminated C/C, bundle C/C

Fig.2 Fiber efficiency of monofilament & bundle C/C composites

Series of experiments on interfacial strength of C/C composites revealed that the existence of surrounding fibers around the fiber of interest, which was measured interfacial strength, reduces residual thermal stress on the fiber of interest at the interface. In other words, high local volume fraction is one of the reasons for the high interfacial strength in C/C composites.

Two possible ways can be derived from above-mentioned results to increase in the fiber efficiency by reducing interfacial strength of C/C composites, as schematically shown in Fig. 1. One is to decrease intrinsic interfacial strength by making fiber surface treatments, which have been often employed in case of ceramic matrix composites. Though the original composite strength follows the ROM assuming fiber strength of $0.3\sigma_f$ because of low fiber efficiency of 30%, it will ideally follow the ROM assuming fiber strength as σ_f , which will result in drastic increase in tensile strength, as shown by the up-pointing arrow in Fig.3.

The other possible way is simpler and less expensive. The residual thermal stress around fibers will be increased by increasing in fiber spacing evenly in C/C composites, meaning reduction in the volume fraction of fiber (V_f), which is expected to reduce apparent interfacial strength in C/C composites.

In this paper, therefore, an attempt was made to improve the fiber efficiency of C/C composites by incorporating carbon black (CB) in the matrix to make the fiber spacing wider as schematically shown in Fig.4.

2 Experimental procedures

The carbon fiber used in this experiment was a PAN based carbon fiber bundle (T300, 6000 filaments, Toray Co.), and carbon matrix was derived from phenolic resin (PR-9640, Sumitomo Bakelite Co.) through conventional resin-char process. Carbon black (NICABEADS; Nippon carbon Co.) (0, 10, 20wt%) was incorporated in phenolic resin diluted with acetone. Bundle C/C composites, reinforced by one fiber bundle, were fabricated by previously reported process [1].

Tensile tests were carried out on the bundle C/C composite specimens with gauge length of 100 mm as shown in Fig.5. The both ends of the bundle C/C

composite were fixed in the steel pipes by the expanding cement.

Fig.3 Possible ways to enhance tensile strength of C/C composites.

Fig. 4 Control of fiber spacing by carbon black incorporation. (a) Conventional C/C composite without CB, (b) CB incorporated C/C composite

Fig. 5 Tensile test specimen of bundle C/C composite.

Tensile tests were carried out with crosshead speed of 0.1 mm/min. Load-displacement curves were obtained by measuring gauge-section displacement of the specimens using non-contact type extension meter. Tensile strength obtained by the experiments was compared by the fiber efficiency calculated by the following equation.

$$Y = \frac{P}{\sigma_{sf} S_f N} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where P is fracture load obtained by the experiments, σ_{sf} is tensile strength of monofilament carbon fiber, S_f is cross sectional area of the carbon fiber, and N is the number of fibers in the composite. After the tensile tests, fracture surface were observed by SEM to clarify the fracture mode.

3 Results and Discussion

Figure 6 shows microstructures of C/C composites with 0 wt% and 20 wt% of CB. As shown in (a), there were almost no fiber spacing, and many fibers were observed contacted each other when C/C composites were fabricated without CB. The C/C composites with 20 wt% CB in the matrix were observed as shown in (b). Holes observed in the figure were caused by detaching of CB particles during polishing. It should be noted that the fiber spacing was obviously increased by incorporating CB particles. Some of the fibers, however, remained close even after incorporating CB particles. Further improvement in the CB incorporation process is expected to get more uniform distribution of carbon fiber in the composites.

In the tensile tests, all kinds of C/C composites with and without CB showed linear elastic behavior up to the final fracture. The fiber efficiency was calculated from experimental results by equation (1), and plotted in Fig.7. In case of C/C composite without CB, the fiber efficiency was significantly low around 8%. This was much lower than previously reported results obtained using pitch based carbon fibers [1,2]. Tentative experimental results on the interfacial shear strength of this composites were 50 - 60 MPa, which was higher than previous results. This must be one of the reasons for significantly low fiber efficiency.

Fig.6 Microstructure of C/C composites
(a) CB 0wt%, (b) CB 20wt%

Fig.7 Effect of carbon black addition on fiber efficiency of C/C composites.

Though the fiber efficiency was remained in the same even after 10 wt% incorporation of CB particles, it was increased up to 10 % with 20 wt % of CB incorporation.

Fracture appearance of each type of specimen was shown in Fig.8. In case of the C/C composite without CB (a), flat fracture surface was observed, which was similar appearance reported in the previous paper [1,2], clearly indicating brittle

Fig. 4 Fracture appearances of C/C composites.
(a) CB 0wt%, (b) CB 10wt%, (c) CB 20wt%

fracture. When the CB was incorporated 10 wt% (b), fracture appearance was obviously changed into “rough surface”. It was observed, however, that some fibers fractured at the same time in a brittle manner.

Fracture mode was further changed from “rough surface” to “independent fibrous-fracture” by incorporating 20 wt% CB.

As shown in these figures, fracture appearance obviously changed by incorporating CB particle. These results are believed to indicate that reduction of interfacial strength is possible by the incorporation of CB particle at least in principle, though the absolute increased value of the fiber efficiency is rather small.

4. Conclusion

Based on the concept for reducing interfacial strength by increasing in fiber spacing, C/C composites were fabricated by incorporating CB particles in the matrix. Fracture appearances after tensile tests were clearly observed that CB particles obviously affected on the fracture modes, and changed it from “brittle” to “fibrous”. In addition, the fiber efficiency was increased with 20 wt% of CB particles from 8 to 10%. With these results, it is expected that reduction of interfacial strength is possible by the incorporation of CB particle at least in principle, and tensile strength will be increased as a result.

References

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